

Notes on the butterfly crab spider *Trichopagis manicata* Simon, 1886 in South Africa (Aranea: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT. *Trichopagis manicata* Simon, 1886 is an African species described from Madagascar. It is rare and known from only a few localities in Madagascar, Gabon, Guinea and South Africa. The aim of this paper is to add notes on their morphology based on images of living spiders, and to provide information on behaviour and distribution.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large numbers of arachnid specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). One of the species was identified as *Trichopagis manicata* Simon, 1886. Several photographs were also submitted by the public as part of the SANSA Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

The genus *Trichopagis* Simon, 1886 is monotypic and data on the type species *T. manicata* described by Simon (1886) from Madagascar (World Spider Catalog, 2022) is limited to three old papers by Simon (1886, 1895) and Millot (1942). It is a rare spider known from a few localities in Gabon, Guinea, and now South Africa. For the first time, images of live specimens of *T. manicata* were available. The aim of this paper is to add notes on the morphology of *T. manicata* based on images of live spiders, with notes on their behaviour and distribution.

METHODS

The voucher specimens of *T. manicata* sampled during SANSA surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria.

TAXONOMY

Trichopagis manicata Simon, 1886

Trichopagis manicata Simon, 1886: 185 (m); Simon, 1895: 1043; Millot, 1942: 62 (m).

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: TL female 5–7 mm, male 4–5 mm. The genus is recognised by the large, dark, club-shaped setae situated in the eye region (Figs 4–5) and on the posterior end of the abdomen (Figs 1 & 6). Carapace semi-circular, as wide as long, and narrowed in eye region (Figs 2 & 13); integument smooth; pale yellow to translucent with a faint greenish tint and thin white marginal band (Fig. 2); eye region covered with a broad red-brown band that extends posteriorly from lateral corners to posterior border (Figs 1 & 3) or sometimes only with two spots (Fig. 15). Eyes in two rows with anterior row narrower than posterior row; the median eyes smaller than the lateral eyes; lateral eyes on small tubercles (Figs 2–3). Carapace provided with two very strong black depressed lanceolate setae at the frontal carapace corners; as well as two similar setae opposite the posterior lateral eyes (Figs 4–5); however, these setae are easily lost. Clypeus with narrow white band; chelicerae brown with dense setae (Fig. 2).

Figs 1–3. *Trichopagis manicata*: 1. Female from Kloof. 2. Female showing eye pattern. 3. Female from Kloof anterior view. Photos: Bruce Blake.

Figures 4–8. *Trichopagis manicata*: 4. Eye pattern showing feathery setae. 5. Male habitus dorsal view. 6. Posterior end of abdomen showing feathery setae. 7. Leg I. 8. Male palp ventral view. 9. Palp retrotibial apophysis (Line drawings 5–9 after Millot, 1942). 10. Female palp (Line drawing after Simon, 1895). 11. Male palp lateral view. 12. Tarsi leg I. 13. Habitus male dorsal view. 14. Habitus male ventral view. Photos: 11–14. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Abdomen longer than wide, with greater width in the posterior third, abdomen shape varies from narrow (Fig. 5) to almost triangular (Figs 1 & 15). Abdomen same pale background as carapace but dorsum decorated with large yellowish brown marking following the contour of the abdomen; colour varies between rich brown to more fawnish brown; two darker spots medially; abdomen ventrally with dark band (Fig. 14); posterior end bears dark club-shaped setae (Fig. 6) that are easily lost. Sternum heart shaped without markings. Legs same colour as carapace; legs I and II in male with distal end of femur and patella dark as well as distal end of tibia and metatarsus (Figs 7, 13–14); tibia and metatarsi I and II with numerous strong paired setae. Palp large with long retrotibial apophysis (Figs 8–9 & 11). Simon (1895) provided a drawing of the thickened tarsi of the palp of a female. In Figs 1–3 & 15–16 the enlarged yellow tarsi could be seen bearing a few strong setae on the border.

Variation: Some colour variation was observed in markings on the carapace and abdomen of the immature specimens from Ndumo; the markings on the carapace consist only of two spots (Fig. 15)

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Gabon, Guinea, South Africa, Madagascar.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

KwaZulu-Natal: iSimangaliso Wetland Park; Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.8843, 32.2534); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83). **Limpopo:** Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.25). **Mpumalanga:** Hector-spruit (-25.43, 31.68).

Figs 11–12. *Trichopagis manicata* immature: 13. Habitus ,dorsal view. 14. Close-up of eye region and swollen palpi. Photos: Peter Webb.

LIFESTYLE

Trichopagis manicata is a free-living plant dweller sampled from trees and shrubs. It was occasionally found inside flower corollas. Also found on trees and low vegetation. It was sampled in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES

This is a rare species. There are no significant threats to this species. Protected in Kosi Bay Nature Reserve, Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2009), Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006), and Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2016). Due to its wide range it is listed as Least Concern. No conservation actions are recommended.

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